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TRANSFER OF SCIENCE-INTENSIVE AND HIGH-TECH PRODUCTS AND TECHNOLOGIES ACROSS CIVIL AND MILITARY PRODUCTION COMPLEXES

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Abstract. *The article addresses the urgent and important problem of efficient use of budgetary funds allocated for funding applied scientific research for the account of transfer of science-intensive and high-tech products and technologies across civil and military industries. The Soviet and foreign conversion experience is analysed, and the impact of market reforms on the science-intensive and high-tech sector of the Russian economy is shown. The current state of science-intensive and high-technology defence enterprises is assessed; conceptual models for guaranteed demand and diffusion of products and technologies are proposed. The developed mechanism for the transfer of products and technologies will contribute to the increased efficiency of budget costs, reduced import dependence and the vitalisation of innovation activity in the economy.*

Keywords: *transfer, conversion, diffusion, innovations, import dependence, production complex, information/analytical base, conceptual model, market reforms.*

Introduction.

Despite numerous problematic situations at the international level, the threat of a large-scale armed conflict is still in the background. Russia's possession of a powerful defence industry complex (DIC) producing high-quality armament systems, as well as nuclear weapons and means of their delivery practically counter-balances any forceful resolution of conflicts with our country. That is why a different kind of war is being waged against Russia – economic, financial, infor-

mational, and only a strong economy with a serious innovative potential can resist aggression of this kind. Currently, Russia is facing unprecedented pressure from a number of industrialised countries represented by restrictions on the purchase of high-tech equipment, devices, materials, etc. [16]. At present, DIC enterprises remain practically the only source of scientific/technical information and technological knowledge. The process of transfer of science-intensive and high-technology products to the civil sector of the economy is one of the most important at the present stage; therefore, it requires accelerated development, financial and institutional consolidation as well as economic protection of the basic DIC industries [2, 3, 7].

Industry conversion experience in the USSR.

Conversion is a managed process of implementing projects characterised by production of civil or dual-use goods by DIC enterprises [10] operating, in particular, in the aerospace and aviation industry. They have unique equipment and technologies that can be used for the production of civilian goods [4]. Among the numerous differing options for using military-technology products in the civilian sphere, the conversion of aerospace equipment seems to be the most logical and efficient solution to the problems of funding the innovation process. The first stage of conversion of the national defence industry complex was started almost immediately after the end of the Great Patriotic War. The enterprises that had previously produced armament, uniforms, ammunition and military equipment switched to the production of civilian goods quickly enough. Civilian aircraft based on long-range bombers, which included the world's first jet passenger aircraft Tu-104, appeared in aviation. This civilian aircraft constructed on the basis of the long-range bomber Tu-16 was the world's only jet passenger airliner for two years. The engineering and technological work started following the decree of the USSR Council of Ministers as of 11 June 1954, and a year later, on 17 June 1955, the Tu-104 took its first flight. After testing and modification of particular units and assemblies, the aircraft entered full production in 1956 and became used for regular domestic flights. Already in 1957, the Tu-104 operated international flights to Prague, London, Delhi, Ottawa and other cities of the world. The spread of innovative technologies was going at a high pace. The production of aeroplanes was established within two years at three aircraft plants located in Kharkov, Kazan and Omsk. The Tu-114 turboprop, converted from the Tu-95 long-range bomber aircraft, was another aircraft within the conversion policy. The engineering work began in 1955; the first flight took place in 1957; regular flights were started in 1961. The Tu-114 passenger aircraft was considered at that time to be the largest and fastest among the world turboprop airliners. The projects to create the IL-76TD-90A civil transport aircraft based on the military IL-76, as well as MI-8 and Mi-26 helicopters which were successfully used not only for military purposes but also for the national economy, proved to be successful.

The military and civilian areas in missilery appeared to be quite close in operational nature. The R7 ballistic missile was originally designed as a combat missile and was intended for the delivery of nuclear ammunition over considerable distances. After modernisation, the ballistic missile began to be used as a carrier vehicle for launching spacecraft into the Earth orbit. It can be noted that civilian equipment was built at DIC enterprises in parallel with military equipment, and the initial stage of the innovation cycle ranged from two years in aviation to four years in rocket engineering. Owing to the peculiarities of the administrative command system which secured quite efficient control over the use of resources, the country was able to take a leading position in the high-tech sectors of the world economy within a fairly short span of time. Among the factors that contributed to the success, one should note military discipline at strategic facilities along with immense personal responsibility for the appropriate fulfilment of planned assignments on the part of head executives at all levels of management.

The impact of market reforms on the science-intensive and high-technology sector of the Russian economy.

The market reforms enabled the enterprises to be in full command of their resources, and capital began to shift to the sectors of the economy in which due conditions were created to maximise returns with minimal risks. Almost all Russian educational institutions set up faculties, departments and courses that trained specialists in trade, finance, law and management to the detriment of engineering specialities. Thus, by the time of the world economy's entry into the sixth wave of innovation, the science-intensive sector of the Russian economy found itself in fact without due funding, without qualified staff, but with a backward material and technical infrastructure and enormous debts to banks and other financial structures. By the beginning of the 21st century, many enterprises in fundamental industries had been devastated and taken over by foreign corporations, or converted into shopping, entertainment, warehousing and office centres [11, 12].

As a result of the total privatisation, a number of enterprises strategically important for the Russian economy were parcelled, and the established scientific and production ties were broken. Many enterprises were no longer able to comply with their targets and had to focus on the purchase of foreign equipment, materials and components [9].

Current state of science-intensive and high-technology DIC enterprises.

One of the few surviving enterprises of the science-intensive and high-tech sector of the economy were research organisations and institutions that were part of the defence industry complex and had innovative potential; therefore, it would have been both erroneous and irrational to ignore their production capacities in modern conditions [8].

In the present conditions, the Russian defence industry complex is one of the most important elements of supporting the innovative activity of enterprises and

organisations of different types of incorporation and those engaged in varying types of economic activity. DIC enterprises can act both as a technological donor and a customer of services, materials and components necessary for the production of armaments, civilian and dual-purpose goods [6].

A prerequisite for the existence of any enterprise is the demand for its products or services. A long-term contract with a DIC enterprise unambiguously increases the civil company's investment attractiveness and favours the inflow of qualified specialists. These factors significantly increase the likelihood of meeting the terms of a contract with a DIC enterprise efficiently and on time.

A positive aspect is a fact that private companies carry out research and development on their own or order R&D from research organisations. In this case, government spending allocated for financing of applied research is saved. By guaranteeing a private company's due sale of products and services to DIC enterprises, the state can provide substantial support to small and medium-sized businesses involved in the realisation of a government's defence order. The enterprises commissioned with a state defence order acquire financial stability so much necessary in crisis conditions [19]. The main products consumed by DIC enterprises quite extensively include various engineering and paintwork materials, electronic devices, microchips and other hardware components, transport vehicles, engines, electric machines, etc. The state support of small and medium-sized enterprises is provided through the procurement of certain services for military organisations. High-tech services that can be provided by private companies to various governmental agencies include communications, information and transport services, repair and maintenance of machinery, buildings and structures, etc.

Information services are of special importance; they include Earth surface observation, meteorological forecasts, monitoring of social media, Internet resources, sociological research, etc.

Many military and other governmental agencies abroad cooperate quite extensively with private companies providing space communication and Earth remote sensing services [15]. For instance, the specifics of the NATO operational ways are that military bases located on all continents of the planet as well as naval ships at sea need stable communication with command centres and with each other. To ensure reliable interaction between specific units, the governments of a number of countries and the bloc's command bodies, it was decided to engage private companies in organising reliable and sustainable communications. In addition, a decision was taken on the possibility of using information obtained from commercial satellites. This way the state, through guaranteed contracts, provided support to private enterprises engaged in the development and construction of artificial Earth satellites as well as to communication providers and surface monitoring firms.

Guaranteed demand model.

Interaction of private companies, governmental agencies and DIC enterprises can be formalised through conceptual and economic/mathematical models of state-guaranteed demand. A characteristic feature of such models is the transfer of civilian products and technologies to the defence industry complex (and vice versa), which significantly increases the efficiency of using state-budget funds.

One of the weak points of such a model is the possible threat of the leak of classified information from civilian facilities belonging to the defence industry and directly to the security structures. One should also remember that the stability of governmental demand is influenced by many internal and external factors, such as the military and political situation in the world, fiscal position, the situation in the global financial markets, etc. To be able to comply with the terms of the contract, the enterprise should have advanced scientific and industrial potential and sustainable relations with suppliers of services, materials and components [18].

The functioning of science-intensive and high-technology sectors forming the defence industry complex is distinguished by their closed nature, when advanced products and technologies developed at the expense of the state budget are usually applied only at the developer enterprise and are not known to other DIC enterprises, not to mention the civil sector of the economy. In modern conditions of accelerated innovative development, the rate of spread of new types of products, technologies and methods in the economic system is of great importance [5]. The current situation does not make it possible to fully disclose the innovation potential of the economy; therefore, three main tasks should be handled to solve this problem. Firstly, it is necessary to create an information base for products and technologies that are crucial for the civilian sector of the economy. The second target is to adapt military items and technologies for use in the industrial production of the civilian sector. The third task is to organise legal and economic protection of the adapted innovative products and technologies.

The model for diffusion of DIC products and technologies into the civilian sector of the economy.

This model should demonstrate the interrelation and interaction of innovation activity actors. The key element of the model is the centre for adaptation of articles and technologies where, at the first stage, an expert commission selects promising DIC products for transfer to the civilian sector. At the next stage, the centre's specialists, together with the developers, adapt products and technologies earlier used at the enterprise that used to be part of the defence industry complex. The obtained results of the technological and development work are protected by patents and included in the information base [1] of DIC products adapted to the civilian sector.

The second element of the model is the technical investment centre whose functions include facilitating the conclusion of leasing agreements for the transfer of equipment and documentation.

At this stage, it is necessary as well to implement a system of product and technology database management based on the Information life-cycle management (ILM) methodology [20]. According to this system, the most relevant scientific and technical information should automatically be shifted to the highest-priority, fastest and most secure bloc [13]. Respectively, less important information is transferred to a cheaper and slower system. This will significantly save the costs of information storage and processing and facilitate the user's search for necessary information [14].

Private enterprises interested in the new technology, jointly with the developers, then finalise the technical preparation for the production of civilian goods.

Technically, the process of transferring the adapted DIC articles and technologies to the civilian sector is implemented through the sale of licences or the use of leasing schemes.

The following technology transfer order is proposed:

- the civilian enterprise searches for and finds a suitable object in the database of DIC articles and technologies adapted to the civil sector of the economy;
- the specialists of the product and technology adaptation centre, following the company's request, modify, jointly with the customer, the selected product to meet the latter's requirements;
- licensing agreements and leasing contracts are concluded with the assistance of the technical investment centre;
- the company pays for and receives necessary technical documentation, equipment as well as loans for the development and production of the new product.

Licensing agreements should provide for payments in the form of royalties subsidising a portion of the enterprise's licence acquisition costs.

Special attention should be paid to the economic and legal protection of innovative projects involving conversion-policy products and technologies. Talking of economic protection, it is most rational to use property insurance against possible innovation risks [17]. The main and truly complicated problem is the organisation of legal protection of conversion-based products and technologies. Intellectual property obtained at a discounted price can be illegally resold to competitors or even moved out of the country. A private enterprise possessing new conversion-based products and technologies can be artificially brought to the brink of bankruptcy and acquired together with its patents by foreign transnational corporations. To prevent this, restrictions should be placed on all mergers and acquisitions for the duration of the conversion licence.

Conclusion.

The analysis shows the high efficiency of the use of military products and technologies in the civilian sector of the economy compared to the development of civil technical objects from inception. Conversion-policy projects require much less time and resources for their realisation.

Currently, there are quite a few examples of successful implementation of military product and technology conversion projects. Special attention should be paid to the modernisation of ballistic missiles which were redesigned into several carrier vehicles of different classes, among them Rokot and Dnepr. The work over the construction of carrier vehicles was commenced in the early 1990s. Despite the devastating consequences of the reforms for the space industry, converted missiles with commercial load on board were launched already after a span of eight years. Meanwhile, the work on the engineering design and testing of the new Angara carrier vehicle has yet to be fully completed. A similar situation is observed with aircraft machinery. Tupolev aircraft were taking to the skies already a year after conversion, while the development of the MS-21 and the SSJ-100 aircraft was going on for decades.

Currently, the civilian sector of the economy successfully uses many types of machinery and services that were originally designed for military purposes – GLONASS global navigation system, satellite communications, systems for monitoring and sensing of the earth's surface and the world ocean, and many other areas. National DIC enterprises have impressive potential in the sphere of technologies for processing and development of new materials; they develop advanced technical solutions in the field of power engineering, transport vehicles, surveillance and communications, etc. This potential is not yet fully used in the civilian sector of the economy. The target of the transfer is to make new technical solutions available to a wide range of consumers without compromising the country's security. The approaches proposed in this article for the extended use in the civilian sector of the economy of products and technologies created in the defence industry complex will make it possible to reduce government spending and increase the resilience of the economic system to external exposure. In addition, this will result in reduced import dependence due to the inflow of high-quality domestic goods and services to local markets. The proposals for the institution of a technology adaptation centre will enable small and medium-sized businesses that do not have sufficient resources for the production of high-tech and science-intensive goods to acquire modern equipment, technical documentation and financing to the required extent. The model of transfer of military-purpose products and technologies to the civilian sector proposed in this article makes it possible to control material and financial flows specific to conversion processes.

In general, the mechanism of transfer of DIC articles and technologies developed by the authors is supposed to increase the efficiency of government spending, reduce import dependence and enhance innovation activities in the economy.

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